

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

THE EFFECTIVENESS OF THE INTEGRATED USE OF ENZYME MEDICATION "PROTOSUBTILIN G3x" AND "CELLOLUX-F" IN QUAIL BREEDING

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Article Received: March 2019

Accepted: April 2019

Published: May 2019

Abstract:

Comprehensive usage of such medications as "Protosubtilin G3x" and "Cellulux-F" is suggested in order to improve the efficiency of meat production and its quality. To achieve this goal, we conducted studies in the foothills of the North Caucasus in the period from 2013 to 2015. During the experiment, we formed four groups of 50 quails in each: the I – control group, which was fed with standard combined fodder recommended by All-Russian research and technological Institute of poultry; the II experimental group of quails – for which 0.03% "Protosubtilin G3x" was given with combined fodder»; the III experimental group of quails – for which 0.02% "Protosubtilin G3x" + 0.007% " Cellulux-F " were added to the combined fodder, the IV experimental group - in addition to their main diet received 0.01%"Cellulux-F". Against the background of the use of the studied medications, the number of red blood cells in the blood of quails of the first, second and third experimental groups was higher than among analogues from the control group on the 14th day by 1,06; 3,18; 4,24%, on the 28th day-1,9; 0,3; 2,7%, on the 56th day-3,7; 2,4; 6%. The number of white blood cells in the blood of quails of the first, second and third experimental groups was higher in comparison with the control group on the 14th day by 5,3; 3,9; 5,7%, on the 28th day - 5,3; 4,5; 6,8%, on the 56th day-3,7; 7,7; 4%. The content of hemoglobin in quails of the first, second and third experimental groups was higher than among analogues from the control group, respectively, on the 14th day by 0,9; 1,6; 1,1%, on the 28th day by 2,3; 3,9; 3,8%, on the 56th day by 0,2; 0,9; 2%. The number of eosinophils in the third experimental group decreased by 10%, and in the first group - 5% in comparison with the control group. Integrated use of such medications as "Protosubtilin G3x" and "Cellulux-F" contributes to a significant increase in the live weight and average daily gain of young quails; the pre-slaughtering weight of quails of the experimental group increased by 12,05; 3,79 and of 10,03%. The average mass of gutted quail carcass was higher in the experimental groups by 11,8, 3,43 and 10,03%. The protein content per 100 g of dry matter is higher in the first group, in the experimental groups by 0,35; 0,07; 0,26% compared with analogues from the control group. The fat content per 100 g of dry matter in the first, second and third experimental groups is lower than in the control group by 2; 0,42; 0,76%, respectively. The mass of edible parts of the carcass is higher in the experimental groups by 18,77; 7,32 and 15,05%, respectively. At the same time, there was no negative impact of the complex use of these medications on the quality of quail meat.

Keywords: quail, red blood cells, hemoglobin, leukocytes, enzyme medications, live weight, meat productivity, meat quality.

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Please cite this article in press Gogaev Oleg Kazbekovich et al., *The Effectiveness Of The Integrated Use Of Enzyme Medication "Protosubtilin G3x" And "Cellulux-F" In Quail Breeding., Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2019; 06(05).*

INTRODUCTION:

High rates of the world production of poultry products are largely associated with the latest achievements in the field of genetics, breeding, feeding, technology content and veterinary protection. Thus, modern crosses have a huge genetic potential for growth and effective feed conversion [1].

The poultry industry of our country provides for a further increase in the range of products. Quail breeding as the developing branch of poultry farming, allows to expand the range of poultry products at the expense of production of highly nutritious food – quail eggs and meat [2]. There is a number of advantages of this branch of poultry farming, before other branches on productive qualities and technology of cultivation. These facts include high precocity, short incubation period, high meat and egg production and small size [3-12].

Reducing feed costs is the most important task, since 70% of the costs in poultry farming fall on them [13], therefore, the support of the digestive system with the help of an optimal complex of feed additives, among which an important role is assigned to enzyme preparations is of great interest [14].

In connection with the urgency of this problem, the task of research was to study the effect of the complex use of enzyme medications "Protosubtilin G3x" and "Cellolux-F" on the biological and meat productivity of quails.

"Protosubtilin G3x" is a powder colored from beige to light brown. The powder form provides uniform distribution of the enzyme in the feed, rapid dissolution and active interaction with protein components, which is an advantage over granular forms. The product is fully compatible with feed components. It is produced on the basis of *Bacillus subtilis* culture by microbial synthesis. It contains in its composition a naturally balanced complex of neutral and alkaline prostheses and related enzymes: β -amylase, β -glucanase, xylanase, lipase.

Cellolux-F contains a blend of enzymes that provides a graded splitting of cellulose, xylans, beta-glucans of plant cell affecting the absorption and utilization of nutrients. Improves the microbiological environment of the intestine by reducing viscosity and increasing the level of monosaccharides.

All the enzymes included in the composition Cellolux-F are the most active in conditions of the animals' digestive system (pH3,5-6,0 and the temperature of 35-400 C).

Cellolux-a contains cellulase complexes (2000±200 u/g), xylanase up to 8000 u/g, glucanase up to 1500 u/g. Catalyzes the breakdown of cellulose, xylans, beta-glucans of plant cells to readily available sugars.

To solve this goal, we conducted studies on the basis of the faculty of Veterinary Medicine and Veterinary and Sanitary Examination of the Mountain state agrarian University in LLC "EcoDom" Vladikavkaz RSO-Alania in the period from 2013 to 2017.

Objects of research were quails of Japanese breed and two feed additives "Protosubtilin G3x" and "Cellolux-F".

During the research we conducted one scientific experiment. The technology of Keeping quail recommended by All-Russian research and technological Institute of poultry was taken as the basis, which includes farming quail for meat to 56 days.

To conduct the experiment, we formed four groups of 50 quails in each: the I – control group, which was fed with standard feed, recommended by All-Russian research and technological Institute of Poultry; the II experimental group – was given 0.03% "Protosubtilin G3x" with feed; the III experimental group – in their feed we added 0.02% "Protosubtilin G3x" + 0.007% "Cellolux-F" and the IV experimental group - received 0.01% "Cellolux-F" in addition to the main diet (table 1).

Table 1. The Scheme of the Experiment

Groups	The number of Quails in the Group	Feeding Features
Control group	100	Complete feed
The 1 experimental group	100	Complete feed + 0,03% "Protosubtilin G3h"
The 2 experimental group	100	Complete feed +0,02% "Protosubtilin G3x" + 0,007% "Cellolux-F"
The 3 experimental group	100	Complete feed +0,01% "Cellullux-F"

Technological parameters of the experimental bird content (temperature, air humidity, gas content, etc.) corresponded the necessary requirements.

Blood quickly reflects the changes occurring in the body, both in normal and in pathology. Blood, while preserving the constancy of the composition, is a very labile system. In connection with which hematological tests are widely used in the practice of veterinary medicine and animal husbandry (tab.2).

Against the background of the use of the studied medications, the number of red blood cells in the

blood of quails of the first, second and third experimental groups was higher than analogues from the control on the 14th day by 1,06; 3,18; 4,24%, on the 28th day-1,9; 0,3; 2,7%, on the 56th day-3,7; 2,4; 6%.

The number of white blood cells in the blood was higher in quails of the first, second and third experimental groups compared with the control group on the 14th day by 5,3; 3,9; 5,7%, on the 28th day-5,3; 4,5; 6,8%, on the 56th day-3,7; 7,7; 4%.

Table 2. Morphological Parameters of Quails' Blood

Group	Age, days	Blood count		
		Red blood cells, $10^{12} / l$	Leukocytes, $10^9 / l$	Hemoglobin, g / l
Control group	14	3,77±0,025	28,1±1,16	88,3±1,36
	28	3,66±0,031	26,3±1,29	84,2±1,38
	56	3,45±0,026	24,4±1,21	83,4±1,44
The 1 experimental group	14	3,81±0,029*	29,6±1,25	89,1±1,56
	28	3,73±0,033	27,7±0,99*	86,2±1,39
	56	3,58±0,028*	25,3±1,05	83,6±1,52
The 2 experimental group	14	3,89±0,021**	29,2±1,08*	89,7±1,29
	28	3,67±0,034	27,5±1,11	87,5±1,47
	56	3,52±0,027	26,3±1,24	84,2±1,48
The 3 experimental group	14	3,93±0,038**	29,7±0,98*	89,3±1,37
	28	3,76±0,039	28,1±0,96	87,4±1,32
	56	3,61±0,032*	25,4±1,2	85,1±1,56

Примечание: *разница достоверна при $P \leq 0,05$, ** $P \leq 0,01$.

Note: * the difference is significant at $P \leq 0,05$, ** $P \leq 0,01$.

The content of hemoglobin in quails of the first, the second and the third experimental groups was higher than the analog around the control, respectively, on the 14th day 0,9; 1,6; 1,1%, on the 28th day 2,3; 3,9; 3,8%, on the 56th day 0,2; 0,9; 2%. Their number corresponded to standard indicators for this type of a bird.

The study of the leukocyte profile of quail blood in the application of enzyme preparations "Protosubtilin G3x" and "Cellolux-F" allows us to note some features. Despite the fact that the ratio of certain types of leukocytes was within physiological

boundaries, the number of eosinophils in the third experimental group decreased by 10%, and in the first by 5% compared with the control group. The content of basophils in the control and experimental groups was the same. The number of neutrophils in all experimental groups was by 5.2% lower than in the control group. The content of lymphocytes was higher in the first and third experimental groups by 3.2%, and in the second experimental group by 2% compared with the control group. The number of monocytes in the first experimental group was lower by 5.9%, and in the second experimental group it was higher by 5.9% compared to the control analogues.

Table 3. Leukocyte Formula of Quails Blood, %

Age, days	Basophis	Eosinophils	Neutrophils	Lymphocytes	Monocytes
Control group					
14	1	6	27	61	5
28	1	7	25	61	6
56	1	7	25	61	6
The 1 experimental group					
14	1	6	25	63	5
28	1	6	24	63	6
56	1	7	24	63	5
The 2 experimental group					
14	1	6	25	62	6
28	1	7	24	62	6
56	1	7	24	62	6
The 3 experimental group					
14	1	6	25	63	5
28	1	6	24	63	6
56	1	6	24	63	6

In the process of conducting research we weekly determined the live weight of quails weighing them on the electronic scales.

Safety, live weight and average daily growth are presented in table 4 and indicate the positive impact of the use of medications on the growth, development and safety of experimental young quails for the entire period of experience.

So, in the 7-days age, against the background of the use of medications, the experimental group slightly

exceeded the control group in terms of live weight. In the first experimental group, this figure was higher by 6,14% compared with the control group. And by the end of the studies, in 56 days, the control group was inferior to the experimental groups by 12,05; 3,79; 10,03%, respectively.

The best results were obtained in the first experimental group, where the bird received enzyme preparations "Protosubtilin G3x" and "Cellolux-F".

Table 4. Safety, Dynamics of Growth and Development of Young Quails

Age, days	A Group of Quail							
	Control group		The 1 experimental group		The 2 experimental group		The 3experimental group	
	Live weight, g	Average daily growth, g	Live weight, g	Average daily growth, g	Live weight, g	Average daily growth, g	Live weight, g	Average daily growth, g
1	8,84 ± 0,095	-	8,92 ± 0,12	-	8,94± 0,11	-	8,81± 0,098	-
7	37,75 ± 0,96	4,13	40,07 ± 1,11	4,45	39,74 ± 1,01	4,40	40,45 ± 0,99	4,52
14	67,29 ± 1,68	4,22	74,93 ± 1,67	4,98	71,66 ± 1,55	4,56	74,19 ± 1,61	4,82
21	96,83 ± 1,91	4,31	108,88 ± 1,88	4,85	101,97 ± 1,79	4,33	108,7 ± 1,94	4,93
28	127 ± 2,03	4,55	144,23 ± 1,93	5,05	134,31 ± 1,99	4,62	143,63 ± 2,01	4,99
35	158,85 ± 2,76	4,56	177,55 ± 2,69	4,76	167,99 ± 2,81	4,74	177,51 ± 2,73	4,84
42	190,77 ± 3,05	4,52	212,41 ± 3,12	4,98	200,96 ± 3,02	4,71	209,43 ± 3,11	4,56
49	222,2 ± 3,33	4,49	247,55 ± 3,58	5,02	231,5 ± 3,43	4,5	243,66 ± 3,61	4,89
56	252,44 ± 3,89	4,32	282,27 ± 4,01	4,96	262,02 ± 3,97	4,36	277,75 ± 4,03	4,87
Safety, %	95		100		100		95	

According to the average daily increments, throughout the experiment, the experimental groups also surpassed the control group and in 56-days age surpassed analogues from the control group by 14,81; 3,79; 12,73%, respectively. The best for this indicator was the first experimental group, where the average daily growth was 282,27, which is 29,83 g or 14,81%. Safety in all groups was at a high level.

Live weight, meat qualities of a bird at a slaughtering age, and also nutritional value of meat are the indicators characterizing meat productivity of a bird.

The final assessment of meat productivity can be made only after slaughtering and anatomical cutting of poultry carcasses with the subsequent chemical analysis of meat.

Table 5 shows the results of anatomical cutting of quail carcasses.

Table 5. Indicators of Meat Productivity of Quails

Indicators		A group of quails			
		Control group	The 1 experimental group	The 2 experimental group	The 3 experimental group
Pre-slaughtering weight of 1 quail, g		252,44±3,89	282,27±4,01	261,1±3,97	277,75±4,03
Weight of eviscerated carcass, g		200,34±2,94	228,97±3,03	207,75±2,99	224,86±2,86
Slaughtering output, %		79,36	81,12	79,57	80,96
Weight of edible parts of the carcass only, g		90,19±2,36	107,12±2,54	96,79±2,31	103,76±2,69
including muscle mass, g	chest	55,24±2,31	65,88±2,22	60,34±2,42	63,77±2,38
	thighs	19,77±1,19	23,68±1,28	20,63±1,21	22,83±1,31
	legs	12,85±0,74	14,37±0,85	13,08±0,82	13,8±0,99
Weight of internal organs, g	heart	2,02±0,009	2,23±0,009	2,08±0,012	2,18±0,011
	liver	4,07±0,018	4,21±0,025	4,11±0,022	4,17±0,019
	reins	1,01±0,016	1,09±0,016	1,02±0,019	1,07±0,02
	lung	2,01±0,031	2,16±0,041	2,07±0,029	2,11±0,032
	lien	2,06±0,039	2,16±0,036	2,09±0,031	2,13±0,04
Weight of down and feather, g		10,03±0,28	11,25±0,23	10,93±0,3	11,06±0,22

From the data of table 5 it is seen that as a result of control slaughtering in the first, second and third experimental groups the average mass of gutted quail carcass is more than in the control group by 11,8; 3,43; 10,03%. The mass of edible parts of the carcass is higher in the experimental groups by 18,77; 7,32; 15,05%, respectively. Thus, the mass of the pectoral muscles is greater in the first, second and third experimental groups compared to the control group by 19,26; 9,23; 15,14%. Mass of femoral muscles - 19,78; 4,35; 15,48%. Shin mass - 11,83; 1,79; 7,39%, respectively.

An indicator of carcass quality, carcass yield is. The quails of the experimental group it reached 81,12; 79,57 and 80,96%, 1,76; of 0.21 and 1.6% more compared to the control group.

In order to determine the effect of enzyme preparations "Protosubtilin G3x" and "Cellolux-F" on the development of internal organs of experimental quails, after the control slaughtering we determined the mass of internal organs.

These data shows that in the experimental groups, compared with analogues from the control group, the mass of internal organs was higher. Thus, the mass of the heart is greater in the experimental groups by 10,39; 2,97; 7,92%. Liver weight is-3,44; 0,98; 2,46%. Lung weight is - 7,46; 2,98; 4,97%. Kidney weight is-7,92; 0,99; 5,94%. Spleen weight is -4,85; 1,46; 3,39%, respectively. The weight of the feather and down is higher in the first, second and third experimental groups in comparison with the control groups by 12,16; 8,97; 10,27%.

The morphological composition of poultry carcasses has some features. Bones of a bird's skeleton are thin and easy, but very strong. The bones of the skull, spine, chest, pelvis, wings, legs form the skeleton of a bird. Their spine is soldered. The tubular bones are filled with air, allowing the bird to fly. Birds' muscle tissue is less layered with connective tissue, but it is quite dense, with low fibers.

The percentage of morphological composition of the carcass tissues of the experimental groups slightly differed from the control group (table.6).

Table 6. Morphological Composition of Young Quails' Carcasses

A group of quails	The morphological structure of tissues		
	Muscular, %	Fat, %	Osteal, %
Control group	36,54±0,59	10,74±0,33	13,19±0,47
The 1 experimental group	37,95±0,72	10,63±0,31	13,36±0,51
The 2 experimental group	37,16±0,66	10,65±0,29	13,22±0,41
The 3 experimental group	37,36±0,71	10,52±0,36	13,27±0,44

Thus, the content of muscle tissue in the carcasses of the first, second and third experimental groups was higher by 3,86; 1,69; 2,24% compared to the control group. The content of adipose tissue in the experimental groups was lower than in the control group by 0,09; 0,84; 2,05%. The bone tissue content

in the first, second and third experimental groups was higher by 1,29; 0,23; 0,6% compared to the control analogues.

One of the objective indicators of the nutritional value of meat is its chemical composition.

Table 7 – The Chemical Composition of Young Quails' Meat

Indicators	A Group of Quails			
	Control group	The 1 experimental group	The 2 experimental group	The 3 experimental group
Moisture, %	73,27±1,39	73,02±1,22	73,64±1,37	72,85±1,28
Dry matter, %	26,73±0,61	26,98±0,56	26,36±0,53	27,15±0,62
including: crude protein, %	21,72±0,78	22,18±0,69	21,78±0,82	22,01±0,71
crude fat, %	3,98±0,031	3,94±0,028	3,97±0,033	3,95±0,029
Per 100 g dry matter: protein, g	81,63±0,85	81,92±0,81	81,69±0,79	81,84±0,86
fat, g	14,44±0,32	14,15±0,24	14,38±0,28	14,33±0,29

From the data of table 7 it can be seen that the chemical composition of meat in quails in the control and experimental groups slightly differed. Thus, the moisture content of quails of the control group is higher than that of quails of the first and third experimental groups by 0,34% and 0,57%, but lower than that of quails of the second experimental group by 0,5%. The dry matter content in quails of the control group is less than that of quails of the first and the third experimental groups by 0,93 and 1,57%, but more than that of quails of the second experimental group by 1,38%. Including crude protein in the first, second and third experimental group is higher by 2,12; 0,28; 1,35% compared to the control group.

The content of crude fat in quails of experimental groups is lower than that of the analogues from the control group by 1; 0,25; 0,75%, respectively.

The protein content per 100 g of dry matter is higher in the first group, but in the experimental groups it is higher by 0,35; 0,07; 0,26% compared with analogues from the control group. The fat content per 100 g of dry matter in the first, second and third experimental groups is lower than in the control group by 2; 0,42; 0,76%, respectively.

To determine the quality of quail meat, we conducted a number of studies, the results of which are shown in table 8.

Table 8. Quails' Meat Quality Indicators

the pH of the meat	5,62	5,68	5,64	5,66
Reaction to ammonia with Nessler reagent	hood greenish-yellow, transparent or slightly cloudy			
Reaction to the peroxidase	hood quickly acquires a blue-green color and 2 minutes into brown.			
Acid number of fat, mg (ANF)	0,8	0,8	0,9	0,8
Peroxide number of fat, (% iodine's)	0,1	0,1	0,1	0,1
Microscopy of smears-prints	microflora was not detected			

All the samples of control and experimental groups of quails' meats on all indicators corresponded to veterinary and sanitary indicators. A tasting with organoleptic characteristics indicates the good quality of the meat.

Enzyme medications did not have a negative impact on the biological parameters of quail meat of the experimental groups, as the products of the primary

protein breakdown in the meat were absent. Important indicators, such as the pH of the meat, the reaction to the ammonia, the reaction of peroxidase, acid number, peroxide number, microscopy of smears of meat correspond the requirements of veterinary-sanitary examination.

SUMMARY:

1. Changes in hematological parameters of quails of

experimental groups receiving enzyme preparations are more pronounced than in the control group, but are within the physiological norm.

- Such medications as "Protosubtilin G3x" and "Cellolux-F" contributed to a significant increase in live weight and average daily gain in young quails; pre-slaughtering weight in quail experimental groups increased by 12,05; 3,79 and 10,03%. The average mass of gutted quail carcass was higher in the experimental groups by 11,8, 3,43 and 10,03%. The mass of edible parts of the carcass in the experimental groups is higher by 18,77; 7,32 and 15,05%, respectively. At the same time, there was no negative impact of the complex use of these medications on the quails' meat quality.

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